

Militia, Boko Haram, Banditry, and Infrastructure Bursts: Impacts on Nigerian Energy Systems

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Abstract

Intentional attacks on energy infrastructure by non-state actors are increasing across politically fragile regions, posing significant risks to energy security, economic stability, and environmental sustainability. Framed through the vulnerability-of-vital-energy-systems perspective, this study assesses how militancy, insurgency, and armed banditry disrupt Nigeria’s oil, gas, and electricity infrastructure through sovereignty-type risks, robustness weaknesses, and resilience deficits. Using two primary datasets covering 2009–2025, the study analyses the spatio-temporal evolution of attacks and evaluates their associated economic and environmental consequences. The South-South (Niger Delta) remains the epicentre of oil infrastructure sabotage, with cumulative TNP-related disruption exposure estimated at approximately USD 22.93 billion over 2009–2024 and losses peaking during 2021–2024 amid escalating crude theft and pipeline vandalism. Since 2021, attacks have increasingly targeted electricity transmission infrastructure in the North-East and North-Central zones, reflecting the growing vulnerability of Nigeria’s highly centralised electricity system. Case studies of the 2016 western-axis pipeline disruptions and the 2024 Shiroro transmission-line attack further show how localised disruptions propagate system-wide economic and environmental consequences. Relative to grid electricity supplied from natural gas, diesel- and gasoline-based backup generation exhibited unit electricity costs approximately 3.2–6.0 times higher during prolonged outages and substantially increased CO_{2e} emissions. The findings demonstrate how attacks on critical infrastructure undermine domestic development objectives, increase dependence on emissions-intensive backup generation, and threaten regional energy integration initiatives. The study highlights the importance of decentralised energy systems, resilience-oriented infrastructure planning, and strengthened protection of critical energy corridors in conflict-affected energy systems.

Keywords: Energy infrastructure, Oil and Gas, Nigeria, Energy security, Conflict resilience

1. Introduction

Intentional attacks on energy systems by non-state actors, particularly in politically unstable nations, have increased significantly in recent years with their far-reaching socio-economic and environmental consequences. These attacks—ranging from vandalism and sabotage to theft, piracy, and terrorism—often occur as interconnected events concentrated in specific regions and timeframes, creating distinct zones of vulnerability [1, 2]. By design, modern energy systems are complex and highly interconnected. This increases their exposure to attacks, with potentially severe consequences for economic instability and social well-being [2, 3].

Globally, a historical analysis of this trend reveals a steady rise in terrorist attacks targeting the energy sector. In 2003, for instance, approximately 25% of all terrorist incidents targeted energy infrastructure. This figure increased to 30% by 2007 and to 35% in subsequent years, underscoring a persistent pattern of rising threats to critical energy assets [4]. Notably, organizations such as Al Qaeda [5] and its affiliates have repeatedly targeted energy sector infrastructure and personnel across countries including Iraq, Algeria, Kuwait, Pakistan, Saudi Arabia, and Yemen [6].

Within the African continent, ongoing domestic conflicts and transnational terrorism threaten energy systems. North Africa, a critical energy supplier to Europe—especially to Spain, Italy, and France—has experienced increasing threats from politically motivated attacks by groups such as Al Qaeda in the Islamic Maghreb (AQIM) [4]. Similarly, numerous hotspots of political instability and subnational terrorism have also emerged within Sub-Saharan African countries like the Democratic Republic of Congo, the Central African Republic, Niger, Liberia, Nigeria, and Burundi [7]. In this context, persistent attacks on energy infrastructure not only have economic, social, and environment impacts, but also entrench regional instability and erode investor confidence, ultimately deterring capital flows into the energy landscape. In Nigeria, for instance, where groups such as the Niger Delta militants in the south, as well as the Boko Haram and armed bandits in the north, have repeatedly targeted critical energy assets [6], the consequences are severe, contributing to the divestment of major energy multinationals and an estimated loss of \$40.6 billion in potential foreign direct investment (FDI) in 2020 alone [8]. This underscores how energy insecurity compounds the infrastructure investment gap, widens the access divide, and undermines long-term development not only in Nigeria but also in countries that rely on its energy exports.

This paper focuses on Nigeria due to its energy-driven economy, its persistent structural and institutional constraints, and its position as a regional energy linchpin. First, the country is highly reliant on crude oil production as its main revenue source and remains one of the world’s largest crude oil exporters [9]. Second, despite Nigeria’s potential as an emerging economy with vast resource endowments and demographic potential, the country continues to struggle with persistent challenges, including worsening insecurity

from non-state actors, poverty, and systemic corruption rooted in weak institutional governance. These factors have not only undermined developmental gains, but have also constrained investor confidence and policy effectiveness [10]. Third, Nigeria functions as a regional energy linchpin, with its energy systems serving not only domestic demand but also neighbouring countries. For instance, Niger Republic historically relied on Nigeria for its entire electricity supply [11]. However, this was suspended in 2023 following ECO-WAS sanctions after a military coup[12]. Although supply later resumed, it was slashed by 42%, dropping from 80MW to 46MW [13]. Similarly, Benin sources part of its power from Nigeria [14]. Finally, Nigeria plays a strategic role in regional and transcontinental gas infrastructure development through strategic projects. The Obiafu-Obrikom-Oben (OB3) pipeline [15], spanning 127 km, and the Ajaokuta-Kaduna-Kano (AKK) pipeline [16], extending 614 km, form critical components of the national gas transmission grid, with the AKK pipeline also serving as a foundational segment of the proposed Trans-Saharan Gas Pipeline (TSGP) linking Nigeria to Algeria and Europe [17]. Nigeria is also a core actor in regional integration efforts, particularly through the West African Power Pool (WAPP) project [18], and the West African Gas Pipeline (WAGP) [19]. The WAGP—an integral segment of the proposed Nigeria-Morocco Gas Pipeline (NMGP) [20]—connects natural gas from the Escravos-Lagos to regional markets in Benin, Togo, Ghana, Côte d’Ivoire, Liberia, Sierra Leone, Guinea, Guinea-Bissau, The Gambia, Senegal, Mauritania, and Morocco, serving both industrial and domestic purposes. The pipeline is ultimately envisioned to supply natural gas to Europe. Given Nigeria’s central role in transforming regional energy trade and integration, it is essential to examine the escalating threats to its energy infrastructure. The intensifying activities of non-state actor groups such as Niger Delta militants, Boko Haram, and armed bandits pose significant risks that could undermine both domestic energy stability and cross-border energy cooperation.

To analytically assess the impacts of insecurity on Nigeria’s energy systems, this study adopts Cherp and Jewell’s [21] vulnerability-of-vital-energy-systems framework as its primary analytical lens. Within this perspective, energy security is understood as the low vulnerability of energy systems that support critical economic activity, public welfare, and societal functioning, rather than solely as a question of supply adequacy or market balance. Following [21], vulnerabilities are interpreted through three analytically distinct but interconnected dimensions: sovereignty, robustness, and resilience. Sovereignty risks arise from deliberate, actor-driven threats to energy systems; robustness risks reflect the technical and infrastructural exposure of energy networks to disruption; and resilience relates to the capacity of systems to absorb, recover from, and adapt to disturbances. In this study, this framework is applied to analyse conflict-affected and infrastructure-constrained energy systems such as Nigeria’s, where insecurity emerges not only from physical attacks on infrastructure but also from structural weaknesses and limited recovery capacities.

Against this backdrop, Nigeria’s oil, gas, and electricity infrastructures are concep-

tualised as vital energy systems [21, 22]. In this study, attacks by non-state actors are analysed primarily as sovereignty-type risks because they constitute intentional and politically or economically motivated disruptions to critical infrastructure. At the same time, the centralised configuration of Nigeria’s energy systems, including long pipeline corridors, limited redundancy in electricity transmission networks, and ageing infrastructure, represents a robustness problem that amplifies the consequences of attacks. The prolonged outages, slow restoration processes, and widespread dependence on diesel- and gasoline-based backup generation observed in the case studies further reveal resilience deficits within the energy system. Together, these vulnerabilities generate cascading economic, environmental, and energy supply consequences that extend beyond immediate physical damage. This analytical framing informs the methodological approach adopted in this study by guiding how attack patterns are spatially mapped, how vulnerabilities and impacts are interpreted across energy subsectors, and how case studies are used to evaluate system-wide consequences and policy-relevant risks.

1.1 The emergence of insurgent factions in Nigeria

To understand the escalating security threats to Nigeria’s energy infrastructure, it is critical to examine the dynamics of non-state actor groups across the six geopolitical zones—namely Boko Haram and armed banditry in the North and militancy in the oil-rich South-South—by tracing their historical evolution, ideological underpinnings, and impacts on national and cross-border energy security.

Starting with northern Nigeria, the rise of Islamic insurgency has been fuelled by deep-rooted historical grievances, including marginalization and the imposition of Western education and governance during colonial rule, which may be viewed as antithetical to traditional and local norms. These ideological drivers complicate efforts to secure energy systems and promote inclusive national development [23]. Specifically, Boko Haram, founded by Muhammad Yusuf in 2002, emerged as a dominant militant group advocating for strict Sharia law while rejecting Western education [24, 25]. Since its emergence in North-East Nigeria, Boko Haram has been responsible for extensive violence, resulting in over 35,000 deaths, the displacement of approximately 2.5 million people, and the destruction of key public infrastructure, including schools, healthcare facilities, and electricity grids [23, 24, 26].

As Boko Haram ransacked communities and disrupted socio-economic order, armed banditry also escalated, particularly in northern Nigeria’s rural areas. Specifically, armed banditry in North-West Nigeria has deep historical roots tracking back to the precolonial era, when criminal groups posed threats to trade routes and regional stability. In the post-independence period, the crisis has escalated into a pervasive threat to national security, driven by a complex mix of structural, environmental, and political factors. The root causes include widespread poverty, youth unemployment, and ungoverned spaces compounded by immediate triggers such as climate change-induced migration, competition

over land and gold resources, and breakdown of judicial systems [27]. Between 2018 and 2020, banditry led to over 4,900 deaths and the displacement of hundreds of thousands [27]. In 2019 alone, it resulted in more than 8,000 deaths in Zamfara State, displaced over 200,000 people internally, and forced more than 60,000 to flee to Niger Republic [28, 29]. Consequently, the human and economic toll of this violence continues to destabilize local communities and threatens the broader security and development of the Nigerian state.

While northern Nigeria contends with Boko Haram insurgency and armed banditry, the southern region, South-South specifically, faces persistent threats from Niger Delta militants, who engage in pipeline vandalization and oil theft [30]. The Niger Delta militancy stems from longstanding disputes over resource control and environmental degradation caused by oil exploration. The origin of militancy in the Niger Delta can be traced to Major Jasper Adaka Boro, who in 1966 led the Niger Delta Volunteer Force (NDVF) to demand a fair share of oil wealth for the Niger Delta people. His declaration of the Niger Delta Republic lasted 12 days before being crushed by federal forces, marking the first known armed resistance over resource control in Nigeria [31]. In 2005, the Movement for the Emancipation of the Niger Delta (MEND) demanded a fair distribution of oil revenues and have employed tactics such as kidnappings, pipeline sabotage, and attacks on oil installations [32]. These disruptions have significantly impacted Nigeria’s oil production, frequently preventing the country from meeting its Organization of Petroleum Exporting Countries (OPEC) export quota [33–35].

Despite extensive literature on the history and activities of non-actors in Nigeria, their cumulative impact on the country’s energy infrastructure remains poorly understood and under-explored.

1.2 Previous work and contributions

Previous research has explored the impacts of insecurity on Nigeria’s energy systems, but often through fragmented lenses—focusing either on specific regions or actors—without offering a comprehensive analysis across Nigeria’s diverse energy security landscape. For example, Adebayo *et al.* [36] and Ikejemba *et al.* [37] assessed the causes and consequences of attacks on electricity transmission lines and renewable energy systems, respectively, highlighting the technical vulnerabilities and socio-economic triggers of energy infrastructure vandalism. Although informative, these studies focus largely on technical and community-level disruptions without examining the broader political and security dynamics. On the dimension of terrorism and energy infrastructure, Al Amin [38] introduced the notion of hydroelectric terrorism and Ojewale [39] explored how banditry in northern Nigeria is economically motivated, often linked to illegal mining and arms trafficking. Omenma [40] further argued that Boko Haram’s activities are not purely ideological but are driven by economic incentives, which have impeded oil exploration in the Lake Chad Basin. Research focused on the Niger Delta region has predominantly evaluated attacks on oil and gas infrastructure. Anifowose *et al.* [41] and Jones [33], for example, analysed

attack patterns and the economic implications of pipeline vandalism and oil-related terrorism. Meanwhile, other studies such as Akinola [31], Ezirim [32], Onuoha [42], and Okoli and Orinya [43] emphasized how oil theft and militant violence pose broader threats to national and regional stability. Although these studies offer valuable insights, they treat Boko Haram, Niger Delta militants, or bandits as isolated actors, or focus on specific infrastructure like pipelines or power lines, fragmenting the analysis. While Yeeles and Akporiaye [44] attempt to quantify the broader economic risks posed by insecurity to the energy sector, the study lacks an integrated lens on actor-specific threats across energy types.

What is missing therefore is a comprehensive analysis that accounts for the roles of Boko Haram, bandits, and Niger Delta militants in shaping Nigeria’s energy security landscape. To fill this gap, this study utilizes attack frequency data and existing literature on revenue loss from 2009 to 2025 compiled by the authors to assess the economic and environmental impacts of insecurity on Nigeria’s energy system. It explores how security challenges such as kidnapping, vandalism, oil theft, Boko Haram insurgency, and banditry undermine Nigeria’s energy security by limiting its ability to meet internal energy demand for domestic and industrial purposes, undermine its efforts to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and combat climate injustice, threaten its position as Africa’s largest oil producer, and hinder its potential as a net energy exporter. This is because, to the best of our knowledge, no study synthesizes how these three groups—operating in different geopolitical zones—collectively disrupt Nigeria’s energy systems, its role as a regional player, nor do they comprehensively quantify the social, economic, and environmental consequences resulting from such incidents. In light of this, the study introduces five novel contributions:

- i) It is the first to assess the collective impact of Niger Delta militants, Boko Haram, and armed bandits on Nigeria’s energy systems.
- ii) It presents a novel dataset of energy infrastructure attacks, compiled by the authors, which systematically classifies attacks by type, location, actor, and affected assets, offering empirical insights into the impact of such incidents.
- iii) It provides a risk profile of vulnerable geographical zones and policy recommendations for future capital-intensive energy investments.
- iv) It presents a quantitative analysis evaluating economic, social, and environmental costs of attacks on oil and gas infrastructure as well as power transmission lines.
- v) It explores the implications of Nigeria’s energy security on key regional initiatives—such as the WAPP, transcontinental gas infrastructure projects including the near-completed OB3 and AKK pipelines, the West African Gas Pipeline, and the proposed TSGP and NMGP—highlighting how domestic vulnerabilities affect broader energy integration and export ambitions across West Africa and into Europe.

2. Methodology

Figure 1: **Methodological framework for analysing non-state actor attacks on Nigeria’s energy systems developed by authors.** The framework applies the vulnerability-of-vital-energy-systems lens [21] through two complementary datasets. **Dataset A (2011–2025)** provides georeferenced records of attacks on oil and gas and electricity transmission infrastructure, underpinning the spatio-temporal analysis of vulnerability hotspots and the selection and evaluation of high-impact disruption events. **Dataset B (2009-2024)** documents crude oil and revenue losses due to vandalism and spill incidents and is used exclusively to estimate the economic and environmental costs of pipeline sabotage, including revenue losses, repair costs, and clean-up expenditures. Together, these datasets generate integrated policy-relevant insights across four dimensions: vulnerability hotspots and decentralised energy systems, community engagement and environmental remediation, early-warning and rapid-response capabilities, and resilience-oriented and low-carbon energy planning.

To analyse the multidimensional impacts of insecurity on Nigeria’s energy systems, the study adopts a mixed methods approach grounded in an energy and critical infrastructure resilience framework. As stated in conceptualisation of energy security as the low vulnerability of vital energy systems, the methodology integrates geospatial analysis with

economic and environment impact assessment to analyse how intentional attacks on energy infrastructure translate into system-wide consequences. To achieve this, two primary datasets are compiled to capture the frequency, spatial distribution, and characteristics of attacks on oil, gas, and electricity infrastructure, as well as to estimate their associated economic and environmental impacts. Additionally, two major disruption events affecting Nigeria’s power generation and transmission systems are analysed as detailed case studies to demonstrate how intentional shock events propagate through centralised energy systems, revealing vulnerabilities, cascading effects, and policy-relevant risks. Collectively, these analytical components enable a comprehensive assessment of how insecurity undermines the performance, resilience, and sustainability of Nigeria’s critical energy infrastructure.

The methodological approach is structured into four subsections. Section 2.1 details the compilation and classification of attack events affecting Nigeria’s oil, gas, and electricity infrastructure, including actor type, targeted assets, location, and timing. Section 2.2 presents the spatial and temporal analytical techniques used to identify patterns, trends, and geographical hotspots of vulnerability across the energy systems. Section 2.3 outlines the procedures employed to estimate the economic losses and environmental impacts associated with infrastructure attacks. Finally, Section 2.4 examines two high-impact disruption events in depth to demonstrate how attacks on critical energy infrastructure propagate through heavily centralised systems, generating huge economic, environmental, and energy supply consequences.

2.1 Cataloguing attack incidents

As there are no dedicated national repositories in Nigeria that systematically document energy infrastructure attacks by non-state actors, this study constructs and analyses two original datasets compiled by the authors and made publicly available via Zenodo [45]. Each dataset serves a distinct analytical purpose, reflecting differences in data availability across time periods as well as oil and gas and power sectors.

Although both datasets are documented in one source [45], they are analytically treated distinct inputs in this study due to differences in structure, temporal resolution, and intended use. One dataset provides georeferenced, event-level records suitable for spatial temporal analysis and case study selection, while the other consists of aggregated loss records used exclusively for economic and environmental cost estimation. For clarity and methodological transparency, these datasets are treated as separate datasets throughout the study.

The first dataset, *spatial analysis dataset (2011-2025)*[45, 46], provides georeferenced records of attacks on oil and gas and electricity transmission infrastructure, including oil and gas facilities, transmission towers, substations, and related assets. This dataset draws primarily on the Council on Foreign Relations’ Nigeria Security Tracker, reports from the Transmission Company of Nigeria (TCN), and corroborated domestic and domestic

and international media sources. Owing to its higher spatial resolution and consistency of location reporting, the 2011-2025 dataset is used exclusively for the spatial-temporal mapping of attack patterns in Section 2.2 and as the empirical source for the two-sector case studies in Section 2.4.

The second dataset, the crude and revenue losses (2009-2024) [45, 47] contains annual aggregates of crude oil losses (million barrels) and corresponding monetary values (billion USD) from attacks on oil and gas infrastructure, crude theft and spill incidents, compiled from industry reports and prior studies. This dataset is used solely for the Section 2.3. The differing temporal coverage reflects the relative availability and reliability of historical records for crude loss reporting against power-sector incident geolocation. Historical Nigerian Naira (NGN) and United States Dollars (USD) exchange rates were obtained from the World Bank data [48], ranging from 148 NGN/USD in 2009 to 1500 NGN/USD in 2024. A dedicated dataset summary is provided in Table 1, detailing dataset name, time coverage, energy system, key variables with units, and primary analytical use.

Table 1: Summary of datasets used for analysing energy infrastructure attacks in Nigeria.

Dataset name	Time coverage	Energy system	Key variables (units)	Primary analytical use
Spatial analysis dataset	2011–2025	Oil and Gas and Power transmission infrastructure	Event date; georeferenced location (lat/long); asset type; actor group	Spatio-temporal mapping of attacks, identification of regional hot-spots, and empirical basis for power-sector case studies (Sections 2.2 and 2.4)
Crude and revenue losses dataset	2009–2024	Oil and gas infrastructure	Annual crude losses (million barrels); monetary losses (billion USD); spill incidents	Estimation of economic and environmental costs of crude oil theft, pipeline vandalization, and oil spills (Section 2.3)

For both datasets, attacks were identified using a structured keyword-based extraction process Table 2 applied to peer-reviewed scholarly literature, institutional repositories, and official reports, including [46]. Detailed descriptions of the datasets, compilation procedures, and source integration are provided in our recently published *Data in Brief* article [47]. For the crude losses and attacks dataset (Dataset B), the attack-frequency sources used in the present study are additionally summarised in Table 3, drawing on [35, 49–51]. To support transparency and reproducibility, the raw datasets and python scripts used for filtering and classification are publicly available via Zenodo [45]. Moreover, to improve analytical transparency and reproducibility, the Zenodo repository is organised into clearly labelled directories separating raw input data, processed analytical outputs, analysis code, and graphical outputs. Original datasets are stored within a dedicated `raw_data` directory, while derived analytical outputs and intermediate processed files are maintained separately within `processed_data`. The repository also includes a dedicated `code` directory containing the Python analysis scripts and notebooks used in the study, together with a `figures` directory containing manuscript graphics and visual outputs. Media and report-based sources may exhibit uneven spatial coverage and occasional ambiguity in actor attribution, especially in remote or contested areas. To address these risks, incidents were cross-validated across multiple independent sources where available and actor classification reflects dominant group presence rather than exclusivity in cases of geographic overlap.

Table 2: Keyword-based classification framework for identifying and categorising energy infrastructure attacks across datasets.

Classification Dimension	Category	Keywords / Search Terms
Actor Group	Boko Haram	‘boko haram’, ‘bokoharam’, ‘north east’, ‘North-East’, ‘northeast’
	Niger Delta militants	‘niger delta’, ‘mend’, ‘militants’, ‘south south’, ‘south-south’, ‘niger delta militants’
	Armed bandits	‘bandits’, ‘banditry’, ‘north-central’, ‘north west’, ‘north-west’, ‘northwest’
Energy Infrastructure Criticality	Critical	‘power station’, ‘substation’, ‘pipeline’, ‘transmission tower’, ‘electricity infrastructure’, ‘oil facility’, ‘gas plant’
	High	‘power grid’, ‘oil rig’, ‘flow station’
	Medium	‘vandalism’, ‘oil vessel’, ‘blow up’, ‘oil trucks’, ‘transmission’
	Low	‘oil spill’, ‘oil theft’, ‘oil workers’

2.2 Mapping attack incidents

To assess both spatial and temporal shifts in incidents across Nigeria’s six geopolitical zones, all incidents in the 2011-2025 dataset were geo-referenced and categorized by infrastructure type, focusing on oil and gas as well as electricity transmission assets, including oil and gas flow-stations, oil wells, transmission towers, substations, and associated facilities. This dataset [45] was selected for spatial analysis due to its comparatively higher geographic resolution and consistency in location reporting, as described in Section 2.1.

To examine changes over time while maintaining interpretability, annual incident data were aggregated into two temporal periods: 2011-2020 and 2021-2025. This temporal division reflects a shift in the pattern and intensity of infrastructure attacks observed in recent years, including the increased targeting of power transmission assets following 2021, coinciding with the escalation of armed banditry and renewed insurgent activity. Aggregating incidents into these periods allows for a clear comparison of pre and post-2021 dynamics without over-fragmenting the data.

Spatial aggregation was conducted at the level of Nigeria’s six geopolitical zones, which represent policy-relevant planning units commonly used in national energy infrastructure development, electricity market administration, and security coordination. Mapping attacks at this scale facilitates comparison across regions while aligning the analysis with institutional and regulatory frameworks governing Nigeria’s energy systems.

Geospatial visualisations were produced using QGIS [52], with incident locations projected using WGS 84 coordinate reference system. Attack events were represented as point features and aggregated by geopolitical zone to generate incident counts for each time period. These maps enable identification of regional hotspots and support visual correlation between attack locations and critical energy infrastructure, such as high-voltage transmission lines and power stations.

The spatial patterns revealed through this mapping exercise informed the selection of the two case studies examined in Section 2.4, which represent high-impact disruption events occurring in regions identified as particularly vulnerable to sustained attacks.

2.3 Determining economic and environmental costs

This study estimates the economic and environmental costs of energy infrastructure attacks by focusing on the Trans-Niger Pipeline (TNP) over the period 2009–2024, using the crude losses and attacks dataset described in Section 2.1. The TNP is selected as the analytical focus for several reasons. It is one of Nigeria’s most strategically significant crude oil export pipelines, transporting approximately 450,000 barrels per day from the Niger Delta to the Bonny Export Terminal [53], which is equivalent to approximately 22.5% of Nigeria’s national crude production capacity during the study period. It handles Bonny Light crude, a benchmark grade that is a principal contributor to Nigeria’s export revenues [54]. Critically, the TNP has been among the most frequently targeted pipelines by

non-state actors in the Niger Delta, with repeated sabotage events — including the 2016 Shell force majeure declaration [55] — directly disrupting national crude export capacity [56–58]. Together, these characteristics make the TNP both an economically significant and empirically well-documented case for assessing the broader consequences of pipeline insecurity in Nigeria.

The crude losses dataset (2009–2024) from [45], together with the indicative attack-frequency data summarised in Table 3, provides annual aggregates of crude oil losses expressed in volumetric units (million barrels), associated monetary values (USD billion), and indicative national pipeline attack frequencies linked to pipeline vandalism, crude theft, and sabotage incidents over the study period. These figures represent observed national losses rather than modelled scenarios; crude exports that continued uninterrupted during the same period are not included.

To estimate an indicative level of disruption exposure associated with the Trans-Niger Pipeline (TNP) relative to observed national crude-loss trends, the analysis adopts a capacity-weighted scaling approach using a dimensionless scaling factor s_{TNP} :

$$s_{\text{TNP}} = \frac{Q_{\text{TNP}}}{Q_{\text{national}}} \quad (1)$$

where Q_{TNP} is the estimated throughput capacity of the TNP (barrels/day) and Q_{national} is Nigeria’s approximate national crude production capacity (barrels/day). Both quantities are expressed in the same units, yielding a scaling factor of approximately 0.225. This scaling factor is used as an indicative infrastructure-exposure proxy rather than a direct incident-level attribution of national crude oil losses to the TNP. Accordingly, the resulting estimates should be interpreted as approximate measures of disruption exposure rather than audited accounting values. Because the TNP has historically experienced disproportionately high levels of sabotage and crude-theft activity relative to some other national pipeline corridors, the capacity-weighted scaling factor may either overestimate or underestimate the true share of disruption exposure associated with the pipeline.

Using this scaling approach, indicative TNP-related economic exposure is estimated across three components: revenue losses, repair costs, and environmental clean-up costs. Revenue exposure is estimated as:

$$\text{TNP Revenue Exposure (USD billion)} = \text{Total National Losses (USD billion)} \times s_{\text{TNP}} \quad (2)$$

Repair costs are estimated based on attack frequency and severity, distinguishing between minor and major incidents:

$$\text{Repair Cost (USD)} = (N \times 0.7 \times C_m) + (N \times 0.3 \times C_M) \quad (3)$$

where N represents the indicative national pipeline attack frequency scaled by sTNP to approximate the number of TNP-related disruption incidents, C_m is the unit cost of minor repairs, and C_M is the unit cost of major repairs. The parameter assumptions underlying N , C_m , and C_M are summarised in Table 4. National pipeline attack-frequency data were compiled from multiple published sources covering different time periods. Because the attack-frequency series combines reported incidents, published estimates, and trend-based extrapolations for recent years, it should be interpreted as an indicative rather than exhaustive count of national pipeline vandalism incidents.

Environmental clean-up costs are estimated as:

$$\text{Clean-up Cost (USD)} = B_S \times C_B \quad (4)$$

where B_S denotes barrels spilled and C_B is the clean-up cost per barrel. The spill-rate assumption and clean-up cost parameter are summarised in Table 4.

To analyse temporal trends, losses were aggregated into four sub-periods (2009–2012, 2013–2016, 2017–2020, and 2021–2024), enabling comparison of changes in attack frequency, revenue exposure, and environmental costs over time. Total estimated TNP-related disruption exposure was calculated as the sum of revenue exposure, repair costs, and environmental clean-up costs for each sub-period.

2.4 Case study evaluation of major disruptions

To examine the potential economic and environmental implications of major energy infrastructure disruptions, this study analyses two high-impact power-sector disruption events identified within the 2011–2025 spatial dataset described in Section 2.1. These case studies were selected based on their scale of disruption, temporal separation, and representation of different non-state actor dynamics affecting Nigeria’s electricity transmission system:

- The 2016 western-axis pipeline disruptions refer to the combined impacts of attacks on the Trans-Forcados Pipeline (TFP) and the Escravos–Lagos Pipeline System (ELPS), which together contributed to major gas-supply constraints affecting thermal power generation in Nigeria’s western axis and resulted in an estimated shortfall of 3,132 MW in national power-generation capacity [49].
- The 2024 Shiroro transmission-line attack caused a major two-week outage affecting electricity supply across 17 northern states [59–61].

Together, these events exemplify the vulnerability of Nigeria’s electricity system to deliberate attacks and reflect the spatial hotspots identified in the mapping analysis

presented in Section 2.2. Both events also illustrate the dependence of Nigeria’s highly centralised electricity system on vulnerable transmission and gas-supply corridors, where localised disruptions can propagate rapidly into broader regional outages and increased reliance on backup electricity generation.

For each case study, economic and environmental impacts were evaluated using electricity-load data for Nigeria’s eleven Distribution Companies (DISCOs), aggregated by geopolitical zone. Electricity demand during outage periods was estimated using historical load records reported by the National Bureau of Statistics [62, 63]. The analysis compares the relative cost implications of backup electricity generation during outages and estimates associated CO_{2e} emissions under alternative fuel-use conditions.

Detailed assumptions, outage durations, fuel-conversion parameters, electricity-cost calculations, and emissions factors used in the case-study evaluation are presented alongside the corresponding results in Section 3.3.

3. Results and analysis

This section presents the results of the analysis. It begins by examining the spatio-temporal patterns of energy infrastructure attacks across Nigeria’s six geopolitical zones using the 2011-2025 georeferenced attack dataset Section 3.1. It then evaluates the economic and environmental consequences of pipeline vandalism along the Trans-Niger Pipeline (TNP) using 2009-2024 losses and attacks dataset Section 3.2. Finally, it presents case study results from two major power sector disruption events identified in the 2011-2025 dataset, illustrating the comparative backup electricity cost premiums and emissions implications associated with prolonged large-scale outages Section 3.3.

3.1 Spatio-temporal dynamics of energy infrastructure attacks

Using the 2011-2025 dataset as described in Section 2.1, we identified a total of 161 attack incidents targeting energy-related infrastructure across Nigeria’s six geopolitical zones over the 15-year period. These incidents were georeferenced and analysed to identify temporal trends and regional concentrations of vulnerability.

Figure 2 shows a clear shift in the temporal and sectoral distribution of attacks across the two periods (2011–2020 and 2021–2025). During the earlier period, attack frequency peaked in 2016, largely by reflecting sustained militant activity in the Niger Delta region. Across the full 2011-2025 period, attacks on oil and gas infrastructure accounted for approximately 74% of all recorded incidents (119 out of 161), while attacks targeting electricity transmission infrastructure comprised the remaining 26%.

While oil and gas infrastructure has remained a persistent target throughout the study period, attacks on electricity transmission infrastructure increased sharply after 2021, with 42 incidents recorded between 2021 and 2025, compared to only two incidents during 2011–2020. This represents a substantial increase relative to the low pre-2021 incident baseline,

although part of the observed escalation may also reflect improvements in reporting coverage and the inclusion of more systematic TCN-sourced records in later years.

Figure 2: Spatio-temporal dynamics of energy infrastructure attacks in Nigeria (a) Emerging patterns and peak attack frequency (2011-2020) concentrated on oil and gas infrastructure (shown as red dot, denoted "Oil_Gas") in the Niger Delta; (b) Recent trends from 2021 to 2025 show a sharp rise in attacks targeting of high-voltage transmission lines and electricity stations (shown as black dot, denoted "Power"), with over 40 incidents recorded, representing a substantial increase relative to the low pre-2021 baseline, although part of this trend may also reflect improved reporting coverage in later years.

Spatially, attacks on oil and gas infrastructure are heavily concentrated in the South-South zone, Nigeria's primary oil and gas producing region, where pipelines, flow stations, and oil workers are frequently targeted. The South-West also records notable activity, largely associated with pipeline vandalism. In contrast, attacks on electricity transmission infrastructure are concentrated in the North-East, reflecting sustained insurgent and bandit activity. The North-Central zone has emerged as an increasingly vulnerable corridor in recent years, with attacks affecting transmission lines critical to national grid stability. The South-East exhibits a mixed pattern of attacks on both oil and gas and power infrastructure, while the North-West records fewer incidents overall, though both infrastructure types are affected.

3.2 Economic and environmental costs of pipeline vandalism

This section presents the results of the TNP disruption-exposure framework described in Section 2.3. Before presenting the findings, the principal assumptions underlying each cost component are summarised below. Given the indicative nature of the infrastructure-scaling approach and the simplified assumptions underlying repair and clean-up cost estimation, the resulting figures should be interpreted as approximate exposure estimates rather than audited accounting values. Revenue loss estimates, which account for the largest share of total costs, are grounded in observed national crude loss data; repair and clean-up cost estimates, by contrast, rely on simplified engineering benchmarks and should be treated with particular caution.

3.2.1 Assumptions and parameter values

The capacity-weighted scaling factor used to estimate indicative TNP-related disruption exposure is derived as:

$$s_{\text{TNP}} = \frac{450,000}{2,000,000} = 0.225 \quad (5)$$

representing the TNP’s estimated throughput capacity as a proportion of Nigeria’s approximate national crude production capacity [56–58]. This scaling factor is intended as an indicative infrastructure-exposure proxy rather than a direct incident-level attribution of national crude losses to the TNP.

National pipeline attack-frequency data were compiled from multiple published sources covering different time periods, as summarised in Table 3. Because the series combines reported incidents, published averages, and trend-based estimates for recent years, the resulting values should be interpreted as indicative rather than exhaustive counts of national pipeline vandalism incidents.

The remaining assumptions used in the economic and environmental cost calculations are summarised in Table 4.

3.2.2 Results

Figure 3 shows substantial variation in estimated disruption exposure across the four analytical sub-periods. The 2013–2016 and 2021–2024 periods exhibit the highest estimated total losses, reaching approximately USD 4.68 billion and USD 11.14 billion respectively. The elevated losses observed during 2021–2024 are associated with exceptionally high crude-theft volumes and elevated oil prices, particularly during 2022 when Shell declared force majeure on the TNP itself [55].

Although indicative national attack frequency was higher during 2017–2020 (approximately 5,700 incidents) than during 2021–2024 (approximately 4,600 estimated incid-

Table 3: Indicative national pipeline attack frequency used in repair cost estimation, aggregated by sub-period (2009–2024).

Period	National Attacks	At-	Annual Average	Aver-	Source
2009–2015	5,468		781/yr		[35]
2016	992		992		[49]
2017–2021	7,143		1,429/yr		[50]
2022	Approx. 1,400		Approx. 1,400		Indicative continuation of elevated crude theft activity [64]
2023	Approx. 1,000		Approx. 1,000		Estimated declining trend in pipeline vandalism and crude theft activity [51]
2024	Approx. 750		Approx. 750		Preliminary declining trend estimate based on reported reductions in crude theft activity [65]
Indicative 2009–2024 total	Approx. 16,700		Approx. 1,040/yr		

Note: Attack-frequency values for 2022–2024 represent indicative trend-based estimates rather than comprehensive incident inventories and should therefore be interpreted cautiously.

Table 4: Summary of assumptions for economic and environmental cost estimation associated with TNP disruption exposure.

No.	Assumption	Source
1	Capacity-weighted scaling factor ($s_{\text{TNP}} = 0.225$), derived from estimated TNP throughput capacity (450,000 bpd) relative to Nigeria’s approximate national production capacity (2,000,000 bpd). Used as an indicative infrastructure-exposure proxy rather than a direct incident-level attribution.	[56–58]
2	Approximate repair-cost distribution: 70% minor incidents (USD 100,000 average repair cost), 30% major incidents (USD 1,000,000 average repair cost). These represent simplified engineering approximations; actual repair expenditures may differ substantially.	[42, 66, 67]
3	Environmental clean-up cost estimated at USD 35 per barrel spilled.	[68]
4	Approximate spill rate of 10% of stolen or lost crude oil during sabotage incidents.	[69, 70]

ents), the latter period incurred substantially greater estimated revenue exposure, reflecting the increasing economic cost associated with individual disruption events under higher oil-price conditions. Following the 2016 disruption peak, attack frequency initially declined before rising again during 2017–2020, coinciding with sustained crude-theft activity and renewed infrastructure vandalism across major pipeline corridors.

The broad alignment between attack frequency (red poly-line) and estimated total losses in Figure 3 suggests a general relationship between infrastructure attack intensity and economic disruption exposure. However, the 2021–2024 period also demonstrates that loss magnitude is shaped not only by attack frequency, but also by commodity-price dynamics, operational disruption severity, and evolving crude-theft sophistication.

Figure 3: **Economic and environmental impact of TNP disruption exposure.** Estimated economic losses (stacked bars, USD billions) and indicative national pipeline attack frequency (red poly-line) associated with disruption exposure along the TNP corridor are shown across four time periods: 2009–2012, 2013–2016, 2017–2020, and 2021–2024. Revenue exposure consistently dominates total estimated costs across all periods. The 2021–2024 period exhibits the highest estimated losses, reaching approximately USD 11.14 billion, associated with elevated crude-theft activity and high oil prices during 2022. Attack-frequency data were compiled from Oyewole (2018), Okumagba (2021), and NEITI-related reporting; values for 2022–2024 represent indicative trend-based estimates rather than comprehensive incident inventories.

Estimated revenue exposure from crude oil theft consistently accounts for the largest share of total losses across all periods. Repair costs remain comparatively modest, ranging from approximately USD 0.23–0.48 billion per period, while environmental clean-up costs range between approximately USD 0.12 billion and USD 0.19 billion per period. Although smaller in magnitude, these environmental costs represent persistent liabilities with long-term ecological and social implications for affected communities and ecosystems in the

Niger Delta.

3.3 Case study results for major disruptions

This section presents the economic and emissions results for the two case studies described in Section 2.4. As with the pipeline disruption-exposure estimates, the calculations presented here rely on a number of simplifying assumptions. The analysis assumes full substitution of unmet electricity demand through backup generation, representing an indicative upper-bound estimate of backup electricity costs and associated emissions during prolonged outages. In practice, some households and enterprises reduce or forego electricity consumption during disruptions, which would lower realised economic and environmental burdens.

3.3.1 Assumptions and parameter values

The principal assumptions underlying cost and emissions calculations are summarised in Table 5.

Table 5: Summary of assumptions for cost and emissions calculations in major power-sector disruption events.

No.	Assumption/Estimate	Source
1	Outage durations: 90 days (2016), 14 days (2024) across six geopolitical zones.	[49, 59–61]
2	Fuel efficiencies: Diesel (0.38), Gasoline (0.32), Natural gas (0.50).	[71–73]
3	Energy conversions: Diesel (10.7 kWh/litre), Gasoline (9.6 kWh/-litre), Natural gas (293 kWh/MMBTU).	[74, 75]
4	Zonal fuel prices compiled from National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) records and converted to USD/kWh.	[76]
5	Regional premiums applied to account for insecurity-related logistics costs in the North-East (+10% grid cost; +20% diesel/gasoline prices).	[77, 78]
6	Grid electricity costs: USD 0.08/kWh (2016) and USD 0.15/kWh (2024).	[76]
7	Electricity-load data for eleven Distribution Companies (DISCOs).	[79, 80]
8	CO _{2e} emission factors: Natural gas (0.42 kg/kWh), Diesel (0.79 kg/kWh), Gasoline (1.12 kg/kWh).	[81, 82]

Fuel prices for diesel and gasoline were compiled at the zonal level from the National Bureau of Statistics [76], reflecting regional price differentials. Exchange rates of 305 NGN/USD (2016) and 1,500 NGN/USD (2024) were applied using World Bank data [48]. To account for higher insecurity-related logistics costs in the North-East, a 10% premium was applied to grid electricity costs and a 20% premium to diesel and gasoline prices, consistent with reported regional inflationary pressures [77, 78].

The backup electricity cost premium was calculated as the ratio between the unit cost of backup electricity generation (C_{backup}) and the unit cost of grid electricity (C_{grid}).

Where C_{backup} is the unit cost of diesel- or gasoline-based backup electricity generation and C_{grid} is the unit cost of grid electricity supplied from natural gas.

Environmental impacts were estimated using fuel-specific CO₂e emission factors for natural gas, diesel, and gasoline. Comparative backup-generation costs and associated emissions were calculated at the DISCO level and subsequently aggregated by geopolitical zone.

3.3.2 Results

Figure 4 illustrates that the 2016 western-axis pipeline disruptions imposed substantial backup electricity cost premiums during prolonged outages. Relative to grid electricity supplied from natural gas, diesel-based backup generation exhibited unit electricity costs approximately 3.4–4.5 times higher, while gasoline-based backup generation ranged from 3.2–4.1 times higher. The highest relative backup electricity cost premiums were observed in the North-East and North-West zones due to insecurity-related logistics constraints and regional fuel-price differentials.

These findings illustrate how disruptions affecting a limited number of gas-supply and transmission corridors can propagate rapidly across Nigeria’s highly centralised electricity system, amplifying regional affordability and emissions burdens.

The 2024 Shiroro transmission-line attack, although shorter in duration, produced similarly substantial backup electricity cost premiums. Relative to grid electricity, diesel-based backup generation exhibited unit electricity costs approximately 4.3–6.0 times higher, while gasoline-based backup generation ranged from 4.8–5.0 times higher, highlighting the sensitivity of electricity affordability to transmission-level disruptions.

Environmentally, the South-West and South-South zones exhibited the highest CO₂e emissions under backup-generation scenarios, reflecting both higher electricity demand and greater dependence on fossil-fuel-based backup generation during prolonged outages. Across both case studies, gasoline-based backup generation produced the highest emissions, followed by diesel, while grid electricity consistently exhibited the lowest emissions intensity.

Customer count shown next to gold circles (2016 and 2024 data: yearly average of billed customers).

Figure 4: Backup electricity cost premiums and CO₂e implications during major power-sector disruptions. Estimated backup electricity cost premiums and CO₂e emissions during major grid outages across Nigeria’s six geopolitical zones. Bar plots (left axis) show the relative unit electricity cost of diesel (blue) and gasoline (orange) backup generation compared with grid electricity supplied from natural gas. Line plots (right axis) represent total CO₂e emissions associated with grid (green), diesel (red), and gasoline (purple) electricity generation. Circle size indicates the estimated electricity customer population within each zone. Note the differing emission scales across panels (10⁶ kg CO₂e for 2016 and 10⁵ kg CO₂e for 2024). Regional variation reflects differences in electricity demand, grid reliability, fuel prices, and insecurity-related logistics constraints.

4. Discussion

Drawing on the results presented in Section 3, three interrelated insights emerge regarding the vulnerability of Nigeria’s vital energy systems. First, the evolving spatial concentration of attacks on electricity transmission infrastructure reveals increasing sovereignty-type risks associated with deliberate, actor-driven disruptions to critical energy systems. Second, the scale and persistence of economic and environmental losses linked to pipeline vandalism highlight structural robustness weaknesses within Nigeria’s centralised oil and gas infrastructure. Third, the prolonged outages, elevated backup-electricity cost premiums, and increased emissions observed during major disruption events expose resilience deficits within the country’s electricity system. Together, these findings demonstrate how sovereignty, robustness, and resilience vulnerabilities interact to shape energy insecurity in conflict-affected energy systems such as Nigeria’s.

First, the spatio-temporal analysis in Section 3.1 reveals a clear evolution in the geography and targets of energy infrastructure attacks. While the South-South region remains the hotspot for oil-related attacks—accounting for 74% of such incidents between 2011 and 2025—the North-East and North-Central zones have witnessed a sustained increase in attacks on electricity transmission infrastructure. Over 40 electricity transmission attacks were recorded in these zones during the 2021–2025 period, representing a substantial increase relative to the low pre-2021 incident baseline. However, this apparent escalation should be interpreted cautiously because improvements in reporting coverage and the inclusion of more systematic TCN-sourced records in later years may also contribute to the observed trend. Interpreted through the vulnerability-of-vital-energy-systems framework, these attacks represent an intensification of sovereignty-type risks because they involve deliberate attempts by non-state actors, including Niger Delta militants, Boko Haram, and armed bandits, to disrupt critical infrastructure. At the same time, attacks on long-distance transmission corridors and major pipelines expose underlying robustness weaknesses associated with Nigeria’s highly centralised and low-redundancy energy systems. Such vulnerabilities intensify grid instability and pose significant risks to critical infrastructure projects nearing completion, including the AKK [16] and OB3 [15] pipelines. Beyond domestic impacts, the increasing exposure of transmission corridors also threatens regional energy integration initiatives—including the WAPP [18], WAGP [19], and the proposed TSGP [17] and NMGP [20]—all of which depend on secure and interconnected cross-border energy infrastructure.

Second, the economic and environmental disruption-exposure assessment in Section 3.2 underscores the scale and persistence of losses associated with pipeline vandalism. Between 2009 and 2024, cumulative TNP-related disruption exposure is estimated at approximately USD 22.93 billion, with the highest estimated exposure occurring during the 2021–2024 period (USD 11.14 billion), driven by escalating crude theft volumes and elevated oil prices, particularly in 2022. Revenue exposure associated with stolen or disrupted crude

oil dominates the cost structure, accounting for approximately 91% of total estimated losses and substantially exceeding repair and clean-up expenditures. Viewed through the robustness dimension of the framework, these findings demonstrate how dependence on centralised export-oriented pipeline infrastructure amplifies systemic exposure to disruption. Although indicative national attack frequency was lower during 2021–2024 (approximately 4,600 incidents) than during 2017–2020 (approximately 5,700 incidents), total estimated disruption exposure was substantially higher in the later period, indicating that loss magnitude is increasingly shaped by commodity-price dynamics and theft sophistication rather than attack frequency alone. Environmentally, clean-up costs linked to oil spills along the TNP range from approximately USD 0.12 billion to USD 0.19 billion per period, highlighting the continued burden of chronic pollution in the Niger Delta region. When contextualised against Nigeria’s GDP of approximately USD 375 billion in 2024 [83], and benchmarked against UNEP’s estimated USD 1 billion, 30-year clean-up requirement for Ogoniland [68] and Reuters’ estimate of USD 12 billion for remediation in Bayelsa State alone [84], these figures illustrate the substantial fiscal and environmental strain imposed by sustained pipeline sabotage. Beyond macroeconomic losses, oil spills continue to generate adverse health outcomes and livelihood disruptions in affected communities [85].

Finally, as demonstrated in Section 3.3, the 2016 western-axis pipeline disruptions and the 2024 Shiroro transmission-line disruption illustrate how localised infrastructure failures can propagate system-wide economic and environmental consequences across Nigeria’s electricity system. During these events, diesel- and gasoline-based backup generation exhibited unit electricity costs approximately 3.2–4.5 times and 4.3–6.0 times higher than grid electricity in 2016 and 2024, respectively, with the North-East and North-West experiencing the highest relative backup-electricity cost premiums due to insecurity-related logistics constraints and regional fuel-price differentials [77, 78]. These findings align with broader evidence that unreliable electricity supply imposes severe macroeconomic burdens on Nigeria, with estimated annual losses of USD 26.2 billion [86]. Although realised outage burdens vary because some households and small enterprises reduce or forego electricity consumption during prolonged disruptions, the widespread reliance on expensive backup generation reflects significant resilience deficits within the electricity system. Despite an estimated USD 22 billion spent annually on backup power generation, energy access in Nigeria remains largely unmet [87], disproportionately affecting households and small enterprises and, in some cases, forcing business closures [44, 88]. Environmentally, the case studies show pronounced increases in CO₂e emissions during outages, particularly in high-demand zones such as the South-West and South-South, reflecting heavy dependence on carbon-intensive fuels. These dynamics not only exacerbate energy poverty but also undermine emissions-reduction efforts and compound climate injustice. Taken together, the findings demonstrate how attacks on power infrastructure interact with underlying robustness weaknesses and resilience deficits to generate com-

pound economic, environmental, and energy-security consequences.

4.1 Policy recommendations

To address the intersecting vulnerabilities identified in this study and strengthen the resilience of Nigeria’s vital energy systems, we propose four policy recommendations derived from the observed spatial patterns of attacks, infrastructure exposure, and the quantified economic and environmental consequences discussed in Sections 3 and 4. Framed through the vulnerability-of-vital-energy-systems perspective, these recommendations target three interrelated objectives: reducing exposure to deliberate attacks, lowering structural vulnerabilities within centralised infrastructure systems, and strengthening the capacity of energy systems to absorb and recover from disruptions across the oil, gas, and electricity sectors.

First, in geographical areas identified as high-risk attack hotspots, national energy reforms should prioritise decentralised energy systems, strengthen social contracts between host communities and energy-producing companies, and advance targeted public-private security arrangements for critical infrastructure. The concentration of attacks on long transmission corridors and centralised assets revealed in this study underscores the robustness vulnerabilities of Nigeria’s historically top-heavy energy architecture. Modular power plants, renewable-energy mini-grids, and battery-storage systems offer more conflict-resilient alternatives because they are less dependent on vulnerable long-distance transmission infrastructure and can maintain electricity access during localised disruptions [89]. One notable example is the Maiduguri Emergency Power Plant [90]—a 52 MW gas-fired facility deployed following insurgent attacks on the electricity transmission network—which illustrates how modular systems can enhance system resilience and maintain electricity supply in fragile and conflict-prone regions.

Second, to reduce the recurrent resurgence of violence in oil-producing regions driven by environmental grievances, targeted remediation of legacy pollution zones such as Ogoniland in the Niger Delta remains essential. The study’s findings show that repeated oil spills and pipeline vandalism impose persistent environmental and economic costs, reinforcing local perceptions of injustice and hostility toward energy infrastructure. As suggested by [91], Cluster Development Boards (CDBs) operating within Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) frameworks can facilitate community-led clean-up and trust-building initiatives. Although the Petroleum Industry Act (PIA) 2021 [92] introduces community-oriented provisions, there remains a clear need for context-specific regulatory frameworks that extend beyond the oil and gas sector to include electricity and renewable-energy infrastructure. Such frameworks are necessary to guide environmental remediation, deter infrastructure vandalism, and safeguard both domestic and cross-border energy systems that are critical to regional energy security.

Third, the study’s identification of high economic losses and prolonged outage durations following attacks demonstrates the need for enhanced early-warning and rapid-

response capabilities. Investments in robust security and surveillance technologies—including sensor networks, phasor measurement units, and predictive analytics—can enable real-time detection of pressure anomalies and suspicious activity around pipelines and transmission assets [93], thereby limiting the severity of disruptions. Recent increases in national oil production in 2025 occurred alongside expanded security interventions targeting oil and gas infrastructure, although broader market, regulatory, and geopolitical factors also influence production levels. While such measures may contribute to short-term stabilisation and deterrence, they require rigorous oversight, due diligence, and ethical safeguards to avoid institutional capture or the emergence of new rent-seeking dynamics.

Finally, the severe affordability and emissions impacts identified in the case studies underscore the need to strengthen long-term resilience within Nigeria’s electricity system. The widespread dependence on diesel- and gasoline-based backup generation during prolonged outages reveals limited system redundancy and weak recovery capacity following disruptions. In this context, decentralised renewable-energy mini-grids integrated with battery storage systems could reduce dependence on vulnerable transmission corridors and provide more resilient alternatives for maintaining electricity access during disruptions. Such systems would not only reduce the economic burden associated with fossil-fuel-based backup generation but also support emissions reduction and broader energy-transition objectives. Integrating decentralised resilience planning into future electricity-sector reforms could therefore help address both the robustness and resilience vulnerabilities identified in this study.

4.2 Limitations and future work

Despite the comprehensive scope of this study, several limitations should be acknowledged. First, the analysis is constrained by data availability, reporting consistency, and uneven spatial coverage, particularly for historical attack incidents in remote or conflict-affected regions of Nigeria. Although the study draws on multiple independent sources and applies cross-validation where possible, reliance on reported incidents may result in underestimation of attack frequency and associated impacts, especially where events are unreported, inconsistently documented, or retrospectively reconstructed from media and institutional records. In addition, the observed increase in electricity transmission attacks after 2021 may partly reflect improvements in reporting coverage and the availability of more systematic TCN-sourced incident records in later years.

Second, the estimation of economic and environmental impacts relies on simplified infrastructure-scaling assumptions and indicative engineering approximations. In particular, the capacity-weighted scaling factor used to estimate TNP-related disruption exposure is intended as an indicative infrastructure-exposure proxy rather than a direct incident-level attribution of national crude losses to the Trans-Niger Pipeline. Similarly, repair-cost estimates are based on simplified severity classifications and benchmark engineering assumptions rather than audited expenditure records. The resulting estimates

should therefore be interpreted as approximate disruption-exposure estimates rather than precise accounting values.

Third, the power-sector case studies rely on a full-substitution assumption in which unmet electricity demand during prolonged outages is supplied through diesel- and gasoline-based backup generation. While this assumption provides an indicative upper-bound estimate of backup electricity cost premiums and associated emissions, realised outage burdens may differ substantially because households and enterprises often reduce or forego electricity consumption during disruptions. The analysis therefore does not explicitly model behavioural adaptation, demand suppression, informal coping mechanisms, or partial substitution effects, all of which may influence realised economic and environmental impacts.

Finally, the case-study analysis focuses on two major disruption events and therefore does not capture the full diversity of attack modalities, infrastructure vulnerabilities, or recovery pathways across Nigeria’s energy systems. Although the selected cases are analytically informative and aligned with the spatial patterns identified in the broader dataset, they should not be interpreted as exhaustive representations of all disruption dynamics affecting the Nigerian energy sector.

Future research could address these limitations by leveraging more granular and real-time data on energy infrastructure disruptions, including high-frequency grid performance records, satellite-based monitoring of pipeline activity, and community-level reporting mechanisms. Integrating predictive geospatial modelling, probabilistic risk analysis, and scenario-based resilience assessment could further enhance understanding of how attack risks evolve across space and time. In addition, deeper examination of the organisational structures, motivations, and adaptive capabilities of non-state actors, together with the role of governance quality, institutional trust, and community engagement, would provide valuable insights for designing more targeted and multidimensional resilience strategies for conflict-affected energy systems.

5. Conclusion

This study provides a comprehensive assessment of how activities by non-state actors—particularly militancy, insurgency, and armed banditry—undermine Nigeria’s energy systems through targeted attacks on oil and gas infrastructure as well as power transmission networks. By compiling and analysing two major datasets covering 2009–2025, the study quantifies the economic and environmental impacts of infrastructure attacks and analyses the system-wide consequences of major power-sector disruptions through two illustrative case studies: the 2016 western-axis pipeline disruptions and the 2024 Shiroro transmission-line attack.

The findings reveal a complex interplay between insecurity, infrastructure sabotage, economic loss, and environmental degradation across Nigeria’s vital energy systems. Long-

standing attacks on oil and gas infrastructure in the South-South region, driven by historical grievances and environmental injustice, have resulted in cumulative TNP-related disruption exposure estimated at approximately USD 22.93 billion over 2009–2024, alongside sustained environmental harm from repeated oil spills. At the same time, the spatio-temporal analysis indicates a shift in Nigeria’s energy insecurity landscape, with attacks on electricity transmission infrastructure increasing sharply after 2021, particularly in the North-East and North-Central zones. Interpreted through the vulnerability-of-vital-energy-systems framework, these patterns reflect an intensification of sovereignty-type risks associated with deliberate attacks on critical infrastructure, while also exposing robustness weaknesses linked to Nigeria’s centralised and low-redundancy energy architecture.

The case-study analysis further demonstrates how disruptions to interconnected energy systems generate cascading economic and environmental consequences. The prolonged outages associated with the 2016 western-axis disruptions and the 2024 Shiroro attack increased dependence on expensive and carbon-intensive backup generation, particularly in regions with limited infrastructure redundancy and high insecurity-related logistics costs. These findings reveal significant resilience deficits within Nigeria’s electricity system, where prolonged disruptions are absorbed primarily through diesel- and gasoline-based backup generation rather than through rapid recovery mechanisms or decentralised system redundancy. More broadly, the results demonstrate how insecurity directly undermines environmental sustainability and climate mitigation objectives by increasing reliance on emissions-intensive coping strategies during outages.

Globally, energy infrastructure has increasingly become a strategic target in conflict settings, where attacks on pipelines, transmission networks, and energy-export corridors are used to impose broader economic and social disruption. In Nigeria’s case, repeated attacks on pipelines and electricity infrastructure not only threaten domestic energy access but also undermine regional integration initiatives and investor confidence in future energy infrastructure projects. As the country seeks to expand renewable energy deployment and achieve its climate and energy-access commitments under the National Climate Change Policy (2021–2030), persistent infrastructure insecurity may weaken the long-term viability and bankability of energy investments. Reducing exposure to infrastructure sabotage and strengthening system resilience therefore emerge as important prerequisites for a secure and inclusive energy transition.

Beyond national implications, Nigeria’s role as a regional energy supplier magnifies the consequences of domestic insecurity. As demonstrated by repeated disruptions to the Trans-Niger Pipeline, infrastructure sabotage compromises not only domestic energy availability but also Nigeria’s ability to meet regional export obligations. Similarly, attacks on power transmission corridors increase grid instability and pose risks to regional integration initiatives. Strengthening the resilience of Nigeria’s energy systems is thus essential for both national development and regional energy security.

To address these challenges, the study highlights the importance of risk-sensitive infrastructure planning, decentralised and modular energy systems, strengthened community engagement around critical infrastructure corridors, and enhanced protection of vulnerable transmission and pipeline networks. The findings suggest that improving energy security in conflict-affected settings requires not only protection of physical infrastructure, but also reduction of underlying robustness vulnerabilities and strengthening of system recovery capacity following disruptions. For countries facing similar threats to critical energy assets, Nigeria’s experience provides both a cautionary case and a broader empirical framework for understanding how conflict, infrastructure vulnerability, and energy insecurity interact within fragile energy systems.

Declarations

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Haruna Inuwa: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Alycia Leonard:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Conceptualization. **Stephanie Hirmer:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Conceptualization.

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Data Availability Statement

Links to all data sources and code are available openly and linked in the article.

Declaration of Interests Statement

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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